

PROFESSIONALISMS IN ULUG'BEK HAMDAM'S NOVELS AS LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL UNITY

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Annotation: In this article, words related to the lexicon of professionalisms and crafts are analyzed from a linguoculturological perspective, to be precise, words and terms related to our national and traditional crafts are studied.

Keywords: term, word-term, professionalism, own layer, developed layer, speech styles, linguoculturology.

Individuals communicate with each other in various conditions and all spheres of activity, distinguishing to a considerable extent in the selection and use of lexical, phraseological, grammatical, and phonetic means in speech. It is true that, the selection of linguistic tools within the international language framework has led to various forms of speech expression. Such diverse forms of speech are called speech styles [1].

The main function of a word is communication – facilitating interaction. In literary style, communication also aims to provide aesthetic pleasure to the reader and influence their emotions. As mentioned above, all units of the lexical layer are used in this process [2].

Every language evolves and develops according to its vocabulary range and grammatical structure. In addition, due to the interaction of language communities, one language influences the second language. Due to economic, political, and cultural relations between nations, one language forms peculiarities in the construction of the second language, absorbs it, and merges into its own unity. From this perspective, in the current Uzbek language dictionary, two major layers are distinguished:

- 1) own layer;
- 2) developed layer [3].

By the term "own layer," mainly the lexemes belonging to that language and their derivatives, as well as formations from other languages with their affixes, are understood.

The oldest part of the Uzbek language dictionary consists of common Turkic lexemes. Such lexemes are still used in many Turkic languages. The basis of common Turkic lexemes is formed by one-stemmed basic lexemes like "bosh, qosh, ko'z, qo'l, kel, ket, yot, bo'l, til" etc. In addition, the common Turkic layer in the Uzbek language dictionary includes two-stem basic and derivative lexemes such as "achchiq, kishi, og'iz, og'ir" etc. [4].

The semantic structure of lexemes also indicates their belonging to their own or developed layer. Semantic differentiation mostly belongs to its layer lexemes; the developed lexeme is usually more semantically ambiguous, and for it to be multivalent, such lexemes need to have a long life in the language and spread widely [5].

Moreover, words related to crafts and professions have been the basis of the own layer in the Uzbek language since ancient times.

The language of literary works is not the same as literary language: literary language is one form of literary speech, it is, of course, based on literary language standards. Literary language is relatively free, and deviations from language standards are also observed. In literary works, based on the author's purpose and desires, words related to crafts and professions or certain social dialects are also used parallel to literary speech [6].

Our daily life is closely related to various crafts and professions, each of which differs from the other with its unique characteristics. The units used by these craftsmen form the vocabulary of professional lexicons. The professional lexicon is the names of events related to social labor, whether it be this or that type, production, science, literature, art, etc [7]. The names of professions are also relative concepts like dialects. Depending on which region the owner of the profession comes from, it is possible to include the vocabulary of that profession in the composition of that dialect. For example, the lexicon used by craftsmen belonging to the Fergana dialect may not be used in the Bukhara dialect or may be called differently. Therefore, the professional lexicon forms two parts of the delimited lexicon. When such words are used in literary works, they gain linguistic and cultural significance.

The utilization of vocational lexicon in literary works serves various stylistic purposes, as evident in [8]. In such cases, authors skillfully employ specific terms to precisely describe the characters in the work, thereby indicating their level of expertise. For example:

Ergash aka obro'li universitetlardan birida fizikadan dars beradi, fan nomzodi, bir necha qo'llanmalar, dovrug'i dunyoga ketgan ikki-uch kashfiyot, maqolalalar muallifi edi... [U.Hamdami. Muvozanat.109 p]. In this excerpt, the use of terms such as subject fan nomzodi, qo'llanma, kashfiyot, maqola, etc., highlights the intellectual level and competence of the character in the field.

In U. Hamdam's novel "Muvozanat" words related to the vocational lexicon are also utilized. As we continue reading the work, we aim to elucidate these words.

Oshxonada pishayotgan ovqatning xush bo'yi karidor bo'ylab taralib kelib, dimog'ini qitiqladi. Og'zi so'lakka to'ldi. Chiday olamay oshxona tomon yurdi. Ikki gazo'choqda bittadan qozon qaynayotgandi. [U.Hamdami. Muvozanat.137-p]

Gulshoda o'choqqa o't qalab qozonni osdi. So'ng to'ldirib suv quydi-da, bir chimdim tuz bilan yeti-sakkiz dona kartoshka tashladi... [U.Hamdami. Muvozanat.197-p]

In these excerpts from the novel, terms such as qozon, o'choq, gazo'choq, etc., about the culinary domain, fulfill their linguistic-cultural unity function. Below, we provide their explanations:

"O'choq"—is an Uzbek national mechanism. It is a place with open front and side, equipped for cooking, with a pot installed for cooking." [O.T.I.L.187-p]

"Qozon"—is an item used for cooking various foods, and preparing or heating water. When cooking in a "qozon", the lid fits tightly.[O.T.I.L.232-p]

Mirzaboyning Yunusobodda soldirayotgan imorati Yusufning nazarida bamisoli bir saroy edi. O'ziyam naq o'ttizta usta, shunga yarasha yordamchi g'imirlar edi. Yusufklar tomboshiga lo'mboz bosish baxonasida kelishdi-yu ustalarga ma'qul tushib yana bir oyga qolishdi... [U.Hamdami. Muvozanat.138-p]

In this passage, "usta"—is a skilled craftsman and teacher: a competent professional engaged in any trade or craft. "Ustasolmoq" - to employ a skilled worker; [O.T.I.L.300-b] and "lo'mboz" - a piece of clay kneaded for molding into pots, generally prepared for molding into pots, are terms that reflect professionalism, which only accentuates national identity.

– Yusuf, bolam, yuvg'ichlar keldi, – shivirladi Tursunoy xola. Yusufning vujudi yana titrab ketdi. Nazarida o'g'li o'lmagan-u g'assollar uni yuvib, dafn uchun kafanlab qo'ymoqchidek edilar. Tushga yaqin qabristonga kelishganda, go'rni allaqachon qazib qo'ygan go'rkovlar birovi ketmon, birovi belkurak ko'targancha turardilar... [U.Hamdam. Muvozanat.154-p]

“G'azzol” – in the Arabic language, a person who washes, especially who washes the dead

“Ketmon” - a long-handled gardening tool with a thin metal blade, used mainly for weeding and breaking up soil [O.T.I.L.222-p].

The aforementioned professional terms, utilized in the excerpts, are also employed in the gravediggers' language, showcasing a sense of belonging to the same nation.

The usage of terms related to the vocational lexicon belongs to the domain of limited lexical layers and is employed in literary works for specific stylistic purposes or to familiarize the reader with the characters, thereby bringing them closer to the book. The semantic characteristics of such terms require the same linguistic-cultural unity as the aforementioned examples.

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